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INVESTIGATIONS OF
THE PHOTOCONDUCTIVITY IN HEXAGONAL
SELENIUM SINGLE CRYSTALS

BY

S. O. HEMILÄ and T. O. TUOMI

Laboratory of Technical Physics
Institute of Technology
Otaniemi, Finland

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Preface

This work enlarges upon the preliminary photoconductivity measurements which formed a part of our licentiate works carried out under the leadership of Professor ERKKI LAURILA, member of Finnish Academy. The main results reported here are based on more detailed measurements financed by the Finnish State Committee for Technical Research. We are indebted to Professor Laurila for helpful discussions during the work, and also to Professor TOR STUBB and his selenium research group with whom contacts have been maintained and who kindly provided us with the selenium single crystals used in the measurements. Dr. G. R. PICKETT has been good enough to read through the English.

Abstract

The photoconductance of three hexagonal Se single crystals has been investigated by measuring the d.c. current in the direction of the c -axis with the voltage across the crystal maintained at 10 V. The spectral dependence of the photoconductivity has been determined at 80°K and 300°K. The observed dependence of the steady state photoconductance ΔG^* on the quantum flux F (light intensity divided by quantum energy) at large intensities can be expressed as $\Delta G^* \sim F^{\bar{\alpha}}$ where $\bar{\alpha}$ is a constant between 0.15 and 0.29. The decay of the photoconductance was always very slow and nonexponential. The rise depended very much on the light intensity used. Using a small intensity at 80°K an S -type photoconductance rise curve $\Delta G(t) = \Delta G^* (1 - e^{-(t-t_0)/\tau})$ was obtained with values for the delay time t_0 and the time constant τ as large as several hours. Thermally stimulated trap emptying has been studied during the warming after illumination at 80°K. The temperature corresponding to the maximum of the thermally stimulated conductance curve decreased continuously from 175°K to 95°K with increasing intensity of the previous excitation. Optical quenching has been observed during the decay at 80°K with quantum energies from 0.8 to 1.65 eV when the quantum energy of the primary excitation was 1.85 eV. The results are in good agreement with the barrier model proposed for selenium by STUKE. However, owing to the many unknown parameters in this model the results obtained cannot prove its validity.

1. Introduction

The hexagonal Se single crystal consists of spiral chains with axes parallel to the c -axis. There are several theoretical works concerning the energy band model of Se [1 . . . 4]. The band structure is rather complicated. The valence band consists of two sub-bands, which are either very near or overlap. The conduction band similarly consists of overlapping sub-bands. Considering the quantum mechanical resonance between the chains a proportion of the energy states in the conduction band is shifted into the forbidden band near the valence band causing a fairly high hole density in Se, according to Ref. [4]. These theoretical models have been successfully used in the interpretation of the optical properties of Se [1, 5, 6, 7]. Furthermore certain electric properties of Se, especially the anisotropies, are obviously a result of this ideal band structure. However, several experimental results can be more easily interpreted by invoking imperfections, for example the high hole density in selenium.

Fig. 1. The absorption coefficient of hexagonal Se. Single crystal, polarized light [6, 7, 8], polycrystalline [9], polycrystalline determined by photovoltage measurements [10].

Fig. 1 shows the absorption coefficients of several hexagonal Se samples as a function of the quantum energy (QE) of the incident light [6 . . . 10]. According to Ref. [10] the forbidden energy band of hexagonal Se is about 1.8 eV at 300°K. In the *volume excitation range* (quantum energies $E_v \leq 1.7$ eV) the inverse of the absorption coefficient is larger than 0.1 mm, and the light penetrates into the crystal fairly well. The imperfections seem to have an essential effect in the absorption of light in this QE range, because the absorption coefficients of different specimens vary considerably. In the *surface excitation range* ($E_v > 2$ eV) the light is mainly absorbed in a 0.1μ surface layer (fundamental absorption). When interpreting the photoconductivity results the difference of these two QE ranges is of great importance. The excitation rate f at a depth x from the illuminated surface is given by the formula

$$f(x) = (1 - R) \alpha e^{-\alpha x} F,$$

where F is the incident quantum flux (measured in quanta/cm² s), α is the absorption coefficient and R is the reflexion coefficient. A homogenous excitation ($f \approx \text{const}$) does not exist in our measurements as the crystal thicknesses used are larger than the inverse of the absorption coefficient, but nevertheless in the *volume excitation case* they are still small enough for a mean f to be a useful concept.

In the photoconductance (PC) studies the QE is an important parameter. The average excitation rate f increases with increasing absorption coefficient, which is a function of the QE. This is responsible for the spectral dependence of the PC in the volume excitation range. Besides, different types of excitations are possible, such as excitations to different types of centers. In this case the probabilities of different excitations depend on the QE used. However, if during the illumination the charge carriers in traps are approximately in thermal equilibrium with those in the allowed band, the effects of different types of excitations cannot be distinguished. In this case, as in the case of one excitation type only, it is possible to describe the effects of the QE and the quantum flux merely by the quantity f defined above.

Besides the QE the other important parameters concerned are the incident quantum flux, the temperature, and the time during the rise and the decay of the PC. Explanations of the influence of these parameters on the PC are almost entirely based on the kinetic model of centers in the homogeneous semiconductor [11]. Such a model involves various types of traps and recombination centers, each type described by its energy level, density, and capture cross sections for free electrons and holes. The mobilities of electrons and holes are usually assumed to be constant (as determined by scattering), so the PC is a result of the increase in the current carrier densities alone, which may be calculated according to the model.

In this work the PC of Se single crystals has been studied experimentally. The QE was used as a parameter in order to determine the spectral dependence of the PC, the differences of the volume- and surface-photoconductances and the effects caused by different types of excitations. The other important parameters were the quantum flux and the temperature. Steady state PC dependences, time behaviours, thermally stimulated current dependences and quenching effects during the decay of the PC are the main experimental results. Initially attempts were made to interpret these results according to the theoretical band models of Se and the usual kinetic models of the centers but it was found not possible to explain the results using such models. In the Chapter »Conclusions» an interpretation is made using the barrier model.

2. Experimental Procedure

Most of the PC measurements were carried out with a hexagonal Se single crystal grown from the liquid phase [12, 13 p. 53]. Its dimensions were $4.3 \times 3.0 \times 0.67 \text{ mm}^3$. Unless otherwise stated, the results presented in this paper have been obtained using this crystal (called large crystal). For comparison

two other crystals were used. One with dimensions $4 \times 3 \times 0.5$ mm³ had been grown from the liquid phase and had been previously used in radiation damage experiments [14] (hereafter called irradiated crystal). The other (called needle crystal) had been grown from the gas phase. Its length was 5.5 mm and the area of its sexangular cross section was 0.16 mm². Sharp points observable in a Laue-picture indicated that at least the surface layer of this crystal was nearly perfect.

In all measurements the electric field was in the direction of the hexagonal *c*-axis. To allow electrical contact the ends of the crystals were electrolytically plated with nickel.

The dark conductances G_0 at 300°K and also the dark conductivities σ_0 calculated from them are given for each crystal in Table I.

Table I.

Dark conductances of Se crystals at 300°K.

	$G_0/\mu S$	$\sigma_0/(\mu S \text{ cm}^{-1})$
large crystal	0.8	17
irradiated crystal	0.7	19
needle crystal	0.035	12

The monochromatic light fell perpendicularly on the *c*-axis of the crystal. The QE of the light was varied from 0.5 to 2.8 eV. Most of the measurements were made with a Hilger & Watts monochromator in the QE range of 0.5 to 2.5 eV (the half-width $\Delta\lambda$ was 0.02μ measured at 0.63μ with maximum slit widths used in the PC measurements). Kodak wratten filters were used in the QE range of 2.1 to 2.8 eV where the intensity of the light from the monochromator was rather small. The relative intensity of the light falling on the crystal was measured with a Schwarz thermopile. In the presentation of the results the relative quantum flux values are used. The light source was an incandescent lamp.

The apparatus used is shown in Fig. 2. During measurement of the crystal conductance the d.c. voltage between the contacts was maintained at 10 V. The current was registered on a 10 mV potentiometer recorder. For more accurate measurements of weak photocurrents there was also a compensating circuit (not shown in Fig. 2).

PC measurements were carried out at the temperatures 80°K, 300°K, and 343°K. For investigation of the thermally stimulated current the crystal was warmed with a heating wire. The temperature of the crystal was measured with a copper-constantan thermocouple. Dry argon gas was led into

Fig. 2. The photoconductance measuring apparatus.

the specimen chamber in order to prevent the diffusion of oxygen into the Se crystal.

The conductance during the constant intensity illumination (the growth curve) and the conductance after the illumination had ceased (the decay curve) were both determined along with the QE and the quantum flux of light at the three temperatures mentioned above. The steady state photoconductance is given by

$$\Delta G^* = G^* - G_0,$$

where G^* is the asymptotic value of the conductance growth curve. The quenching of the photoconductance during the decay was studied by means of an infrared light at 80°K. The thermally stimulated conductance, which is the total conductance of the crystal during the warming was measured using different constant warming rates after illumination at 80°K had ceased.

3. Experimental Results

A. Photoconductance as a function of quantum energy

The PC of the large crystal as a function of the QE is shown in Fig. 3. At 300°K the QE 1.67 eV, corresponding to the maximum of the curve, is slightly less than the energy gap of hexagonal Se, which is 1.79 eV at 300°K according to CHOYKE and PATRICK [10]. In the volume excitation range $E_v = 1.0 \dots 1.67$ eV the PC is obviously caused by centers and increases approximately exponentially with increasing QE.

Fig. 3. The photoconductance of Se single crystal as a function of the quantum energy.

In the QE range 1.7 . . . 2.0 eV the PC decreases abruptly. In this region the volume excitation changes to surface excitation (Fig. 1). If the surface recombination velocity is rather high and the diffusion of the photocarriers into the bulk of the material is rather slow then the PC caused by the surface excitation must be much smaller than that caused by the volume excitation (cf. the spectral dependence of the PC of CdS [15]). However, the surface recombination velocity and the diffusion length of the Se single crystals used in these experiments are not known and consequently the reason for this drop in the PC remains uncertain.

When the QE decreases from the value 0.7 eV, the PC increases slightly according to our measurements (Fig. 3) and thus there may be a PC peak at a quantum energy below 0.5 eV. Such a peak would be due to the excitation of holes between the valence sub-bands or to the excitation of electrons from the valence band to centers.

When the temperature decreases from 300°K to 80°K, the QE corresponding to the maximum of the PC increases by about 0.18 eV. This shift is obviously connected with the increase of the energy gap with decreasing temperature [10]. The slope of the spectral dependence curve in the volume excitation range at 80°K is nearly twice that at 300°K.

Allowing for the change of the energy gap with temperature which shifts the PC peak slightly, the PC of the large crystal increased with decreasing temperature. The maximum PC values at the three temperatures are seen in Table II.

Table II.

Maximum of the spectral dependence curve. The quantum flux is constant.

T °K	Large crystal			Irradiated crystal			Needle crystal		
	E_g eV	ΔG^* μS	$\Delta\sigma^*$ $\mu S \text{ cm}^{-1}$	E_g eV	ΔG^* μS	$\Delta\sigma^*$ $\mu S \text{ cm}^{-1}$	E_g eV	ΔG^* μS	$\Delta\sigma^*$ $\mu S \text{ cm}^{-1}$
80	1.85	6.5	140				1.85	0.007	2.5
300	1.67	2.9	60	1.70	1.1	30	1.70	0.07	25
343	1.67	1.9	40						

At 80°K with the same quantum flux as in Fig. 3 ΔG -values greater than $0.1 \mu S$ were observed at quantum energies between 0.7 and 1.1 eV. However, steady state values of the PC and therefore the form of the spectral dependence curve were not obtained because of the large time constants of the PC rise curves.

At 300°K the spectral dependences of the PC of the needle crystal and the irradiated crystal were very similar to that of the large crystal shown in Fig. 3. The maximum photoconductivity values of the three crystals were also of the same order, as seen in Table II. However with decreasing temperature the PC of the needle crystal decreased considerably in contrast to the behaviour of the large crystal (see Table II). The slope of the spectral dependence curve for the needle crystal was very steep at 80°K, the PC at 1.65 eV being only one tenth of the maximum PC at 1.85 eV. A weak excess PC peak existed at about 1.2 eV.

Several determinations of the PC spectral dependence of Se single crystals have been reported in the literature [16, 17, 18]. The quantum energies corresponding to the main maximum of the PC are as follows.

	[16]	[17]	[18]	Large crystal	Needle crystal
80°K	1.84	1.78(93°K)	—	1.85	1.85
300°K	1.75	—	1.55 . . . 1.75	1.67	1.70

According to every report the slope of the PC spectral dependence curve in the volume excitation range is fairly steep at 80°K and steeper than at 300°K. STUKE has observed a low excess peak at 1.2 eV, and this peak increased very strongly with the mechanical deformation of the crystal [17]. As mentioned above, we observed a weak peak at about the same QE using the needle crystal, and the same kind of imperfection photoconductance seems to exist in the large crystal which appears as a small bump on the main peak (Fig. 3).

When going over to the surface excitation range the PC reduces rather strongly at 80°K according to Refs. [16, 17]. We observed this reduction at 80°K and also at 300°K in all three crystals. In thin leaf like crystals *Prosser* has detected a high excess peak in the surface excitation range at 300°K [16].

B. Photoconductance as a function of quantum flux

The steady state PC as a function of the quantum flux was studied in detail in the volume excitation range at 300°K. In Fig. 4 the logarithm of the steady state PC is plotted against the logarithm of the quantum flux. At low light intensities the slope of the curve is about one, but at high intensities it falls to 0.28. This curve was obtained using the most effective QE 1.67 eV. As the QE decreases, the curve shifts to higher quantum fluxes (i.e. to the right) preserving its shape. This can be seen in Fig. 5, where the slopes κ of the curve group $\Delta G^*(F; E_\nu)$ are plotted against the corresponding steady state photoconductances ΔG^* . The logarithmic derivative

$$\kappa(F, E_\nu) = \frac{\partial \log \Delta G^*(F, E_\nu)}{\partial \log F}$$

Fig. 4. The photoconductance of Se single crystal as a function of the quantum flux.

Fig. 5. $\bar{z} = \frac{\partial \log \Delta G^*(F, E)}{\partial \log F}$ versus ΔG^* . Volume excitation range, 300°K. The numbers give the QE values in eV of the corresponding points.

depends approximately on the steady state PC alone. Therefore at all quantum energies in the volume excitation range the dependence $\Delta G^*(F)$ can be characterized by two constants ΔG_d^* and $\bar{z}$. At large photoconductances where $\Delta G^* > \Delta G_d^*$, the derivative $\bar{z}$ is a constant $\bar{z}$, but when the PC decreases below ΔG_d^* the $\bar{z}$ increases continuously. The effect of temperature on the quantities $\bar{z}$ and ΔG_d^* is presented in Table III. The same kind of intensity dependence as in Fig. 4 was observed in the needle crystal. The values of $\bar{z}$ and ΔG_d^* for the needle crystal and the large crystal were approximately the same (see Table III).

Table III.

Photoconductance as a function of quantum flux in the volume excitation range.

	T	$\bar{z}$	$\Delta G_d^*/\mu S$	$\Delta \sigma_d^*/\mu S \text{ cm}^{-1}$
Large crystal	300°K	0.28	0.8	17
	80°K	0.15		Not determined because of the slow PC rise at small intensities
	343°K	≈ 0.3	1.7	36
Needle crystal	300°K	0.22	0.035	12
	80°K	0.2		Not determined

In the surface excitation range the logarithmic derivative $\kappa(F, E_v)$ can also be presented as a function of ΔG^* only. However, the κ corresponding to a given PC value in this range is smaller than that in the volume excitation range. Further, a constant $\kappa = \bar{\kappa}$ was not observed in the case of surface excitation but the PC tended to saturate at $\Delta G^* \approx 0.4 \mu S$ (the smallest κ observed was 0.16 at 300°K).

No quantitative results concerning the dependence of the PC on the light intensity in Se single crystal have been reported in the literature. In Ref. [19] the electric current is given as a function of the voltage with the intensity of the light as a parameter. Measurements were carried out using a rather thin Se single crystal with an electric field perpendicular to the *c*-axis. From these results it is possible to construct the dependence of ΔG^* on *F* at some small voltage. This dependence is qualitatively similar to that in Fig. 4 with $\bar{\kappa} \approx 0.17$ at 300°K.

C. Rise and decay of photoconductance

Three rise and decay curves measured at the different temperatures with a constant QE and quantum flux are shown in Fig. 6. The rise curves can be characterized by a time t_e in which the PC rises to $(1 - 1/e) \cdot \Delta G^* \approx 0.63 \cdot \Delta G^*$. The dependence of t_e on the steady state PC in different crystals is shown in Fig. 7. At large values of the PC t_e is proportional to $(\Delta G^*)^{-r}$ where r is a constant between 2 and 3.

Fig. 6. The rise and decay curves. $E_v = 1.7$ eV, $F = \text{constant}$. The steady state value of the curve measured at 80°K has been calculated from the formula

$$\Delta G = \Delta G^*(1 - e^{-(t-t_0)/\tau}).$$

Fig. 7. The time t_e as a function of the steady state photoconductance. t_e is the time taken to reach 63% of the steady state photoconductance. I, II, and V refer to the large crystal, III to the irradiated crystal (open dots), IV to the needle crystal. The numbers near the points marked $\times$ and $*$ indicate the QE values of the light in eV.

At 80°K the rise curve is S -shaped at all the quantum energies used. Except with high light intensities at 1.85 eV the PC is at first nearly zero for a time t_0 and then increases with time like $\Delta G^*(1 - e^{-(t-t_0)/\tau})$. The delay time t_0 and the time constant τ increase with decreasing quantum flux (cf. Fig. 7). The largest values observed were $t_0 = 3$ h and $\tau = 100$ h.

The decay curves of the PC can in most cases be described approximately by means of a formula

$$G(t) = G^*(1 + t/t_1)^{-n}$$

(for conductances above $G \approx 1.4 G_0$), where $G(t)$ = total conductance and G^* is the (total) steady state conductance and illumination ceases at the time $t = 0$. The value of n is about 0.14 at 300°K in the large crystal as well as in the irradiated crystal measured with the quantum energy 1.7 eV. The exponent n does not depend remarkably on the steady state total

conductance nor on the temperature and the quantum energy of the light. The quantity t_1 is roughly inversely proportional to the quantum flux used (at 300°K) and it falls very remarkably as the temperature increases (in one experiment t_1 at 300°K was about twenty times that at 343°K).

Few qualitative statements about the slow time dependences of the PC are found in the literature. For the decay curves at 80°K one can also use the formula $G(t) = G_1 - a \log \frac{t}{t'}$ when $t \gg t'$ as in the reference [17]. However, the decay of the PC is slower in the crystals used here than in those of [17].

D. Thermally stimulated conductance

Some typical curves of thermally stimulated conductance vs temperature in the volume excitation range are shown in Fig. 8. The following conclusions can be made:

a) When the warming rate w is increased the conductance in the high temperature tail of the curve increases. Curves 2, 3, 4, and 6 with about double the warming rate compared with the others form a separate group.

b) The time interval between the end of the illumination and the beginning of the warming t_{dark} has very little effect. However, when t_{dark} is increased to a value of an hour the conductance in the rising part of the curve (at low temperatures) is reduced. (Compare curve 4 with 2 and curve 8 with 5.)

c) The maximum thermally stimulated conductance G_m depends mainly on the photoconductance G_{max} at the end of the illumination. This dependence is shown in Fig. 9. The measured points fall approximately on the straight line

$$G_m = 1.7 \mu S + 0.6 \cdot G_{\text{max}} .$$

Therefore, the effects of the QE, the quantum flux, and the illumination time (which has effect on the ratio G_{max}/G^*) are all included in the change of one quantity, namely G_{max} . The scatter of the points from the straight line in Fig. 9 is chiefly a result of the slight dependence of G_m on the warming rate and on the dark time.

d) When G_m decreases, the corresponding temperature T_m increases (see Fig. 8). As stated previously G_m increases linearly with increasing photoconductance G_{max} and therefore, the temperature T_m decreases *continuously* with increasing G_{max} . Observed T_m values varied in the range 95 to 175°K.

Fig. 8. The thermally stimulated conductance G as a function of temperature. The maximum photoconductance G_{max} at the end of illumination at $80^{\circ}K$ depends on the quantum flux F , on the quantum energy E_v , and on the illumination time which determines the ratio G_{max}/G^* . During the long illumination the steady state was nearly reached (i.e. $G_{max}/G^* = 0.8 \dots 1.0$) but in some cases only a short light pulse was used ($G_{max}/G^* = 0.3 \dots 0.5$). w is the warming rate and t_{dark} the time interval between the end of the illumination and the beginning of the warming.

e) The thermally stimulated conductance curve was strongly asymmetric. Separate peaks could not be distinguished unambiguously.

In the surface excitation range the thermally stimulated conductance dependence is of the same type as observed in the volume excitation range. However, at a given G_{max} the surface excitation value of G_m seems to be about $0.8 \mu S$ larger than volume excitation value (Fig. 9).

The thermally stimulated conductance was also measured during the stepwise warming of the crystal according to the reference [17]. After an illumination at $80^{\circ}K$ the crystal was warmed at a constant rate to a certain temperature and then cooled down to $80^{\circ}K$ rather quickly. This warming-cooling cycle was repeated ten times increasing the end temperature of the

Fig. 9. The maximum thermally stimulated conductance G_m versus the maximum photoconductance $G_{\max}$ (at the cessation of illumination).

Fig. 10. The thermally stimulated conductance during the stepwise warming of the crystal.

warming period in every cycle. Fig. 10 shows the result of this measurement. For clarity only a few cooling curves have been plotted. For conductances $G > 0.1 \mu S$ all the curves belong to a curve group $G = G_1 e^{-E/kT}$, where $G_1 = 60 \mu S$ ($\sigma_1 = 1.3 \text{ mS cm}^{-1}$). During the experiment E was continuously increased from the value 0.03 eV to the value 0.14 eV. The latter value corresponds to the temperature dependence of the dark conductivity. At the conductances $G < 0.1 \mu S$ the formula given above no longer holds and the conductance increases less with increasing temperature than in the range above $0.1 \mu S$. During the cooling period the conductance decreased slowly (the broken lines in Fig. 10). After the temperature of 80°K was reached the conductance decayed exponentially with a time constant of about 3 min.

The thermally stimulated conductance results for the irradiated crystal were similar to those of the large crystal. In the conductance vs temperature curves of the needle crystal there was no maximum. (As seen in Table II the PC of this crystal was rather small at 80°K). In a typical measurement on this crystal the PC $G_{\text{max}} = 0.01 \mu S$ was created by illumination of a 1.85 eV light at 80°K . During warming in darkness the conductance rose quite rapidly from $0.002 \mu S$ reaching $0.02 \mu S$ at the temperature of 115°K and thereafter increased slowly except in the three ranges 115 to 130°K , 150 to 160°K , and 215 to 230°K where it remained constant. The effects of the light intensity and the warming rate were qualitatively the same as those observed for the large crystal.

Stuke has studied the thermally stimulated current of selenium single crystal [17]. His result obtained from measurements during stepwise warming using a mechanically deformed crystal followed the formula

$$\sigma = \sigma_1 e^{-E/kT}.$$

The value of σ_1 was 1.6 mS cm^{-1} and during the measurement E increased from 0.065 eV to 0.148 eV. In our measurement σ_1 was 1.3 mS cm^{-1} and E increased from 0.03 eV to 0.14 eV. The agreement of these results is fairly good.

E. Optical quenching

Fig. 11 shows qualitatively how the optical quenching during the decay at 80°K depends on the quantum energy of the quenching light. The quenching begins at about 0.75 eV and it is considerable between the quantum energies 1.0 and 1.6 eV. It decreases to zero at 1.85 eV which is the QE of the primary excitation. When the QE of the quenching light is greater than 1.45 eV it also excites. This excitation is clearly observable at 1.65 eV and at 1.75 eV. A quenching measurement with the light of 1.45 eV was also carried out using a quantum flux $\frac{1}{16}$ of that in Fig. 11. It was found that the

Fig. 11. The optical quenching during the decay of the photoconductivity at various quantum energies.

slope of the decay curve immediately after the quenching light was turned on was $\frac{1}{4}$ of the equivalent value in Fig. 11. The quenching also occurred after the primary excitation of 1.65 eV light.

The thermally stimulated conductance curve after quenching was similar to that obtained after illumination with the quenching light alone.

The optical quenching was also observed in the irradiated and in the needle crystal. At the moment the quenching light 1.45 eV was turned on the slope of the decay curve in the large crystal was multiplied by about 25 (in Fig. 11). The corresponding factor in the needle crystal in the same circumstances was about 10.

Using a primary excitation of 1.8 eV Stuke [17] found that in his crystals the quenching during the decay of the photoconductance at 93°K began at 0.9 eV and had its maximum at 1.4 eV. Our results are in good agreement with these.

F. Some other measurements and remarks

The dark conductivity of the Se single crystals depended on the temperature according to the formula $\sigma_0 = \sigma_1 e^{-E_B/kT}$ with E_B -values of Table IV.

Table IV.

E_B values of the temperature dependence of the dark conductivity in the formula

$$\sigma_0 = \sigma_1 \cdot e^{-E_B/kT}.$$

E_B/eV	when $\sigma_0 > 2.1 \mu S \text{ cm}^{-1}$	when $\sigma_0 < 2.2 \mu S \text{ cm}^{-1}$
large crystal	0.14	0.10
irradiated crystal	0.14	0.07
needle crystal	0.21	0.21

The dark current of the selenium single crystal was proportional to the applied voltage U at 300°K in the range $U = 0 \dots 10$ V. The photocurrent was proportional to the power 1.2 of the voltage at 80°K in the same voltage range.

Sudden changes of voltage caused transient effects. When the voltage of 10 V was switched on at 300°K the dark current of the crystal increased to 6 per cent above the equivalent steady state value, G_0 . Then it decayed roughly exponentially with a time constant of about 20 min to G_0 . When the steady state PC $4.7 \mu S (E_\nu = 1.85 \text{ eV})$ was reached at 80°K the voltage was dropped to zero and then again switched on. The PC reached a value which was 8 per cent greater than that obtained before. It then began to decrease to the value $4.7 \mu S$ nearly exponentially with a time constant of about 5 min.

During the decay of the PC with quantum energy 1.85 eV at 80°K the light of the same quantum energy but of a smaller quantum flux caused a transient. After this light was turned on the conductance at first increased, reached a maximum and then decayed slowly towards an asymptotic value. In some circumstances the rise curve of the photoconductance overshoot when measured with the quantum energy 1.85 eV at 80°K. An effect of similar origin occurred at 300°K, when a large quantum flux and $E_\nu = 1.7$ eV was used to obtain a large PC. The rise to 90 per cent of ΔG^* was fast but the full stationary value was reached rather slowly (cf. Chapter 3.C.). During the 20 s interruption of the illumination the PC decayed to a fairly small value. After this interruption the PC rise was *fast up to the steady state value* (however without overshooting).

During the rises and decays at 80°K oscillations of the photoconductance occurred but not regularly. Their amplitude was about $0.1 \mu S$ and their frequency was of the order of 0.1 Hz.

There was a slow decrease of the dark conductance at 300°K during a year. In September 1964 the dark conductance of the large crystal was $1.08 \mu S$ and in September 1965 it was $0.57 \mu S$.

4. Conclusions

It is obvious that there exist some kind of centers in all three Se single crystals used in our measurements. Clearly the photoconductivity observed with quantum energies smaller than the energy gap of hexagonal Se is caused by the excitations of the electrons from the occupied centers to the conduction band or from the valence band to the unoccupied centers. These centers act as deep traps e.g. in the thermally stimulated current phenomenon, in the slow *S*-type photoconductance rise and in the extremely slow decay of the PC. It is impossible to interpret the PC effects observed assuming only one kind of traps with a discrete energy level. Rather the interpretation of the PC results seems to require the assumption that these traps have a continuous or quasicontinuous distribution of energy levels.

At 300°K the charge carriers in the traps of Se seem to be approximately in thermal equilibrium with the carriers in the corresponding allowed band. One can see in Fig. 5, that the state of the crystal, described by the logarithmic derivative κ , is uniquely determined by the steady state PC reached. Therefore, at a given temperature the excitation rate f completely describes the effect of the illumination in the volume excitation range. At liquid nitrogen temperature we can observe effects due to different types of excitations, e.g. the quenching effect and the overshooting mentioned in Chapter 3. F. Thus, at 80°K the effect of the illumination cannot be uniquely described by the one quantity f . However, at 80°K the differences in the distribution of the charge carriers in the traps also have a small effect on most PC dependences, e.g. in the thermally stimulated current curves (Fig. 9).

Various models have been proposed to explain the conductance and PC of Se [1, 5, 6, 17, 13 pp. 1, 35, 109]. Suitable indications for the validity of a model proposed are the following experimental results:

a) The temperature dependence of the dark conductivity is given by

$$\sigma_0 = \sigma_1 e^{-E_B/kT}, \quad E_B \approx 0.14 \text{ eV}$$

according to Refs. [19, 20, 21], and this work.

b) In a.c. measurements the dark conductivity increases rapidly with increasing frequency and at high frequencies the exponential temperature dependence disappears altogether [22, 23].

c) According to the thermoelectric power and a.c. Hall-measurements the hole density in Se seems to be fairly large (about 10^{14} cm^{-3}) and roughly independent of temperature. The thermoelectric power does not depend on the illumination whereas the conductivity is increased by two orders of magnitude [17, 20, 21].

d) After an illumination at low temperature the temperature dependence of the conductivity is still exponential, but the quantity E_B is fairly small.

When warming in steps E_B increases *continuously* to the value corresponding to the dark conductivity, according to Ref. [17] and Fig. 10 in this work.

e) The photoconductivity in the temperature range $80^\circ\text{K} \dots 350^\circ\text{K}$ does not depend strongly (exponentially) on the temperature, according to Ref. 16 and this work. As seen in Table II the PC in the large crystal increases with decreasing temperature, but decreases in the needle crystal.

It is not possible to interpret all these results according to the usual scattering mobility mechanism although one assumes the existence of proper traps or a proper difference between the valence sub-bands with different mobilities. A hopping or tunneling process can explain the dark conductivity results fairly well but the photoconductance results d) and e) cannot be understood on the basis of this mechanism. Therefore some kind of a barrier model seems to be most plausible in interpreting the experimental results mentioned. STUKE has been able to explain the electric effects of Se single crystals using such a model [17].

A barrier model was initially proposed for explaining the PC of PbS layers [24]. The basic idea in this model is that inhomogeneities such as dislocations or grain boundaries form a closed network in the sample. The periodic potential is disturbed in these interfaces, and many impurities have a tendency to collect there. Thus, local energy states and a net charge occur in these regions, and this charge causes a potential wall. If these potential walls act as barriers to the majority carriers then they will essentially determine the conductivity of the sample by restricting the carrier mobility. PETRITZ has derived the following formula for the electric conductivity of a *p*-type sample with barriers

$$\sigma_0 = e \frac{a}{T} e^{-eU_B/kT} p_0,$$

where a depends only on the properties of the barrier, p_0 is the hole density in high conductivity regions and U_B is the height of the potential barriers [24]. The photoconductivity at small intensities is obtained from the differential

$$\Delta\sigma^* = \sigma_0 \Delta p/p_0 + e\mu_n \Delta n + e\sigma_0(-\Delta U_B/kT).$$

We see that although the dark conductivity of the crystal is determined by the barriers there are three possible PC mechanisms, the increase of the hole density, the creation of mobile electrons and finally the lowering of potential barriers. This may occur through the reduction of the net charge caused by the trapping of electrons in the barrier layers themselves.

If we assume that the mobility of the holes in Se is determined by potential barriers and that the PC is caused by the lowering of these barriers then the

Fig. 12. A barrier model used for explanation of experimental photoconductance results of Se. v is the thermal velocity of the electrons, S_n is the capture cross section for free electrons by recombination centers with density N_R , n is the density of free electrons in the high conductivity regions, and n_R is the density of recombination centers occupied by an electron. N_A is the density of the acceptor states and $N(E)$ is the energy distribution of the electron traps.

experimental results a) to d) mentioned above are easily explained. Although there exists a factor $\sigma_0 \sim \exp(-e U_B/kT)$ in the expression of the PC, the temperature dependence of the PC observed (result e) does not disagree with the model, because the escape probability of electrons from the barrier traps decreases exponentially with decreasing temperature.

Fig. 12 shows the barrier model used for the interpretation of the PC results presented in this paper. This model is essentially the same as the one proposed by Stuke [17, 13 s. 35]. Acceptor states with a density N_A at temperatures $T \geq 80^\circ\text{K}$ are nearly fully ionized causing the roughly temperature independent hole density $p_0 \approx N_A$. Donor states with continuous or quasicontinuous energy distribution $N(E)$ are situated inhomogeneously in the crystal. They are also ionized and create potential barriers U_B for holes, the majority carriers. Further, some kind of recombination centers with density N_R exist throughout the crystal. The temperature and frequency dependences of the observed conductivity agree with the model, as also do the space charge limited current dependences [17].

The spectral dependence of the PC agrees qualitatively with this model. The other PC results observed can be explained by the model as follows.

If one supposes an energy state distribution of the traps of the type

$$N(E) = \frac{N_0}{1 + e^{-\frac{E-E_0}{E_1}}}$$

with constants N_0 , E_0 , and E_1 , and a thermal equilibrium between electrons in the traps and in the conduction band, one can calculate a quantum flux dependence of the PC. This calculation gives $\kappa = 1$ at small quantum fluxes and $\kappa = \bar{\kappa}$ (small constant) at large quantum fluxes in agreement with the experimental dependence in Fig. 4. Using the values $E_0 = 1.1$ eV and $E_1 = 0.070$ eV a value $\bar{\kappa} = 0.28$ at 300°K was obtained. Because of the approximative thermal equilibrium $\bar{\kappa}$ depends only on ΔG^* at a given temperature, in agreement with the results given in Fig. 5.

The recombination probability for trapped electrons and holes is assumed to be negligible. Therefore, only electrons excited to the conduction band may recombine through the recombination centers. This recombination is slow because the density of holes is small in the barrier layers and the density of conduction electrons is very small outside the barrier layers. Consequently the decay curves are also extraordinarily slow. The continuous trap distribution results in the nonexponential time dependences, in agreement to the experimental results. The thermal excitation of electrons from the traps to the conduction band becomes more probable when the temperature is increased so that the decay of the PC becomes much faster as the crystal warms, in agreement with the results.

The rise of the PC is fairly fast at high intensities but becomes very slow at small intensities, because in this case only the deepest traps with very small thermal excitation probabilities are occupied in the steady state. At 80°K the excitations have to fill the large proportion of the traps in order to create an observable PC. So the PC rise in linear scale is of *S*-shape.

As the crystal warms after illumination at 80°K the penetration probability of the holes through the barriers increases, and the conductance increases proportionally to the factor $e^{-e U_B/kT}$. Then electrons begin to be excited from the barrier traps and the conductivity decreases (U_B increases). The distribution of electrons in the traps comes to approximate thermal equilibrium by retrapping. So, the thermally stimulated conductance G_m mainly depends on the photoconductance at the end of the illumination $G_{\max}$ only. When $G_{\max}$ increases, the quasi Fermi level of electrons rises and the G_m increases (Fig. 9), but the excitation of the electrons from the shallower traps is easier and so the temperature T_m corresponding to G_m decreases. Also the effects of the dark time t_{dark} and the warming rate w are in agreement with the results presented above.

The thermally stimulated conductance expected from the model when warming the crystal in steps is in good agreement with the experimental results (Fig. 10), as interpreted by Stuke [17].

We assume, that the light is also able to excite the electrons from the traps to the conduction band. After strong illumination at 80°K a large proportion of the traps is filled. After the cessation of this illumination

additional illumination using a smaller QE mainly excites electrons from the traps to the conduction band causing the quenching effect. The time dependences and the effect of QE according to the model agree with the results in Fig. 11.

Strong illumination using a QE of 1.85 eV at 80°K causes a distribution of occupied traps. After the illumination the shallowest traps are quickly emptied. If weaker light with the same QE is now used these shallow traps rapidly become re-occupied to a certain degree while the deep traps continue to empty slowly. Now, if the density of the shallow traps is large enough a maximum in the PC curve occurs, as reported in Chapter 3.F.

One PC result disagrees with the proposed model. As seen in Fig. 10 the slow warming and rapid cooling period caused the increased conductance value at 80°K. However, the total electron density in the traps could not increase during this period. The observed increase in conductivity thus disagrees with the model. Of course, it is possible to interpret this increased conductance either by assuming some additional *hole* traps in the barriers or by assuming an additional PC due to the mobility of the electrons excited to the conduction band.

Nevertheless, the most experimental PC results presented in this paper are in good qualitative agreement with the barrier model used. Unfortunately, because there are many unknown parameters in this model its value is rather small and mere PC measurements cannot give sufficient information to test its validity. However, a consistent interpretation of the PC results is possible on this basis and some further useful measurements are suggested. The results presented here give little information on the energy level distribution of the electron traps. A continuous distribution was assumed in Fig. 12 as most suitable but most measurements could be explained equally well in other ways such as by considering two types of traps with discrete energy levels. The thermally stimulated conductance, the quenching and the PC transient measurements would be the most effective in studying these energy levels.

According to Weisberg [25] an inhomogeneous distribution of imperfections is fairly usual in semiconductors and the effect of these inhomogeneities on the mobility of the charge carriers can be great and thus, the existence of the closed barrier network in Se single crystals is possible. However, the values of some quantities which should depend strongly on the barriers are nearly the same in very different Se crystals. Further the drift mobility of vitreous Se is similar to that of hexagonal Se [26]. This would be easier to understand on the basis of a hopping or tunneling process because of the similarity of the microstructures in the different Se specimens involved. Therefore, although the barrier model may be used with some success, its physical basis is not yet clear.

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